

SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape. In this paper, an annotated species list of spiders species sampled from Jeffreys Bay is presented. A total of 38 families represented by 151 species from 101 genera have been recorded. The most species-rich families are the Araneidae (27 spp.), Thomisidae (23 spp.), and Salticidae (16 spp.). The conservation status and level of endemicity based on their known distribution are provided for each species.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

World-wide, the loss of biodiversity and the increasing growth of the urban world population are some of the main challenges of this century. Interest in the invertebrate fauna of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 20 years. These areas are not just seen as human-modified habitats of low intrinsic biodiversity, but as havens for wildlife in an increasingly intensively farmed and over-managed countryside. These areas can be potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, promoting connectivity between species' meta-populations both within and outside towns and cities.

Unfortunately, the evidence for these effects on spiders in South Africa is either anecdotal or lacking. Little has been published on spiders of urban and suburban areas. Tucker (1920) was the first to report on the spiders of Kirstenbosch in the Western Cape. Other Western Cape studies supported initiatives to remove alien pines in urban areas and highlight the conservation value of urban botanical gardens of indigenous plants (Pryke & Samways, 2009). In Gauteng, one of the surveys in urban areas includes a three-year study at the Rietondale Research Station, an area close to the centre of Pretoria, by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). In Kwa-Zulu-Natal, Clark and Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanical garden in Pietermaritzburg, while Whitmore *et al.* (2002) investigated arthropod diversity on road islands in Durban, where they found that spider abundance was markedly higher on grassy road islands that were regularly mowed than on structurally enhanced road islands. In the Free State, several studies have been undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden, Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). For the Eastern Cape, this is the first report of a spider survey in an urban area.

In the Eastern Cape, several surveys from protected areas have been published (Table 1). Most of the abovementioned surveys form part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) for protected areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

In this paper we present the first SANSA survey on the spider fauna sampled from an urban garden (Fig. 3) and surrounding areas in Jeffreys Bay in the Eastern Cape (Figs 1–2). Information on endemicity and conservation status for 148 species is provided.

Figures 1–3. Jeffreys Bay. 1-2. Noorsekloof. 3. Garden. Photo credits: Linda Wiese.

TABLE 1. Results of SANSA spider surveys in the Eastern Cape

LOCALITY	FAM	SPP	REFERENCES
Mountain Zebra National Park	34	76	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988; 2006
Addo Elephant National Park	47	276	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Mkambati Nature Reserve	29	132	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Silaka Nature Reserve		11	Forbanka & Niba, 2013
Asante Sana Nature Reserve	29	92	Midgley, 2012 (unpublished)
Thyspunt	26	94	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2021
Amathole Mountains	52	321	Haddad <i>et al.</i> (under review)
Jeffreys Bay	38	149	

METHODS

Study area: Jeffreys Bay (JB)(34°2'S 24°55'E, 34°2'S 24°55'E) is a constituent part of the Kouga Local Municipality of the Sarah Baartman District in the Eastern Cape province. The vegetation of the area consists of fynbos and subtropical vegetation known as Valley Bushveld, a broad term given to the subtropical transitional thickets of the Eastern Cape that are mostly seen in the hot, dry valleys of rivers. The vegetation is usually made up of thorny, dense vegetation or succulent shrubs (Figs 1 & 2). At the seashore (Fig. 4) intertidal spiders were sampled.

Figure 4. Survey area Jeffreys Bay, Eastern Cape.

Figure 5. Jeffreys Bay coastline where *Amaurobioides africana* (Anyphaenidae) (Fig. 21) was sampled.

Identification, photography and voucher specimens: Identifications were done in Pretoria by the second author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the NCA at the Agricultural Research Council-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Table 4). The photographs were donated to the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species were determined (Table 3) based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 = when Jeffreys Bay is the type locality.
- 5 = ECE, endemic to the Eastern Cape province but wider than the type locality.

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of Jeffreys Bay listing the total number of families, genera (G), and species (SPP.)

FAMILY	G	SPP.	FAMILY	G	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Anyphaenidae	1	1	Philodromidae	2	2
Araneidae	18	27	Pholcidae	2	3
Cheiracanthiidae	2	4	Phyxelididae	1	2
Clubionidae	1	3	Pisauridae	2	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Prodidomidae	1	1
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	12	16
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Desidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Dictynidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	3
Eresidae	2	2	Stasimopidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	2	5	Tetragnathidae	3	6
Hahniidae	1	2	Theridiidae	7	9
Hersiliidae	1	1	Thomisidae	10	23
Linyphiidae	4	4	Trachelidae	2	2
Lycosidae	3	3	Uloboridae	2	2
Mimetidae	2	3	Zodariidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	3	9	Zoropsidae	1	1
			38	101	151

- 4 = SAE, endemic to South Africa but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 = SAE, South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene rivers).
- 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African endemic).
- 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 151 species from 38 families and 101 genera are presently known from Jeffreys Bay. Nine species could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy is unresolved or it could be new. Two species of the species sampled have already been recognised as new to science: *Cheiramiona lindae* Lotz, 2015 (Fig. 6, Cheiracanthiidae) and *Mystaria lindaicapensis* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (Figs 7–8, Thomisidae). The oxyopid, *Oxyopes dumonti* (Vinson, 1863) was also for the first time recorded from South Africa at Jeffreys Bay (Wiese, 2008, Fig. 34).

Family diversity: Of the 38 spider families collected from Jeffreys Bay (Tables 2 & 4), the Araneidae (27 spp.) followed by the Thomisidae (23 spp.) and Salticidae with 16 species are the most diverse families. Thirteen of the species collected are known from only a single species.

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species recorded from Jeffreys Bay.

CONSERVATION STATUS	No. spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (DD)	9	DD	5.9
Not evaluated (NE)	10	NE	6.2
Least concern (LC)	130	LC	86.0
Vulnerable (V)	1	VU	0.7
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	19	LC	12.5
1 – African endemics (AE)	86	LC	56.9
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	26	LC	17.2
3 – South African endemics (SAE): more than three provinces	20	LC	13.2
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	9	LC	6.0
4 – <i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Easter and Western Cape endemics (ECE)	1	VU	0.7
6 – <i>Cheiramiona lindae</i> Type locality (Jeffreys Bay)	1	DDT	0.7

Conservation status: The majority of species (130; 86%) have a wide distribution and no threats are known and they are listed as Least Concern. Nine species are Data Deficient as some are only known from one sex and other have a very restricted distribution. Ten was not evaluated as some the where immature or taxonomy not resolved.

Cheiramiona lindae (Cheiracanthiidae), an Eastern Cape endemic (Fig. 6), is presently known only from a single male sampled in 2008 in a garden in Jeffreys Bay (Lotz, 2015). Too little is known about the location, habitat, and threats of this species for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed to find the female and determine the species' range. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic purposes.

The thomisid *Mystaria lindaicapensis* (Figs 7 & 8) is a species newly described from the garden in Jeffrey Bay (Honiball Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014). It was also recoded from Knysna but it has a small distribution range (< 20 000 km²) and is regarded as Vulnerable.

Endemism: Nineteen species (12.5%) are wider known than Africa, while 86 species (56.9%) have a wider distribution throughout Africa (AE), with 26 species (17.2 %) known from Southern Africa (STHE) and only 20 (13.2 %) are South African endemics.

Figures 7–8. *Mystaria lindaicapensis*. 7. Female. 8. Male.

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Figures 9–21. 9–20. Araneidae: 9. *Araneus apricus*. 10. *Araneus nigroquadratus*. 11. *Caerostris sexcupidata*. 12. *Cyclosa insulana*. 13. *Cyrtophora citricola*. 14. *Gea infuscata*. 15. *Ideocaira triquetra*. 16. *Isoxya cicatricosa*. 17. *Neoscona quincasea*. 18. *Neoscona alberti*. 19. *Neoscona rufipalpis*. 20. *Zygiella* sp. 21. *Amaurobioides africana* (Anyphaenidae). 22. *Gandanameno spenceri* (Eresidae). 23. *Quamtana vidal* (Pholcidae).

Figures 24–37. Jeffreys Bay spiders. 24–29. Thomisidae: 24. *Phrynarachne rugosa*. 25. *Diaea rohani*. 26. *Tmarus cancellatus*. 27. *Thomisus scrupeus*. 28. *Thomisus daradioides*. 29. *Synema langheldi*. 30. *Euryopis funebris* (Theridiidae). 31. *Philoponella angolensis* (Uloboridae). 32. *Mecynidis dentipalpis* (Linyphiidae). 33. *Phanotea cavata* (Zoropsidae). 34. *Oxyopes dumonti* (Oxyopidae). 35. *Uloborus plumipes* (Uloboridae). 36. *Stasimopus schoenlandi* (Stasimopidae). 37. *Afroceceto martini* (Trachelidae).

TABLE 4: Checklist of the spiders species recorded from Jeffreys Bay in the Eastern Cape with information on their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Amaurobiidae	<i>Chresiona</i> sp.		NE	
Anyphaenidae	<i>Amaurobioides africana</i> Hewitt, 1917	2	LC	STHE
Araneidae	<i>Acusilas africanus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Araneus</i> cf. <i>detrimentosus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)		NE	
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
	<i>Lariniodes</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Neoscona alberti</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona quincasea</i> Roberts, 1983	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zygiella</i> sp. (Clerck, 1757)		NE	
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona amarifontis</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona lindae</i> Lotz, 2015 *type	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona paradisis</i> Lotz, 2003	2	LC	STHE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona godfreyi</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona kiboschensis</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
Corinnidae	<i>Coenopychus tropicalis</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
Ctenidae	<i>Ctenus gulosus</i> Des Arts, 1912	2	LC	STHE
Cyatholipidae	<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	4	LC	SAE
Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
Desidae	<i>Badumna longinqua</i> (L. Koch, 1867)	0	LC	C
Dictynidae	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
Gnaphosidae	<i>Xerophaeus crustosus</i> Purcell, 1907	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Zelotes capsula</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
Hersiliidae	<i>Neotama corticola</i> (Lawrence, 1937)	3	LC	SAE
Linyphiidae	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
Lycosidae	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
Mimetidae	<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ero lawrencei</i> Unzicker, 1966	2	LC	STHE
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa strandi</i> (Lessert, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes dumonti</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
	<i>Peucetia maculifera</i> Pocock, 1900	2	LC	STHE
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus globulifer</i> Simon, 1893	3	DD	SAE
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana vidal</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus dehoop</i> Huber, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole lyra</i> Griswold, 1990	3	LC	SAE
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
Prodidomidae	<i>Theuma schreineri</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE?
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C
	<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phlegra imperiosa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes silvatica</i> Purcell 1904	4	LC	SAE
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna</i> sp.		NE	
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Anyphops stauntoni</i> (Pocock, 1902)	1	LC	AE
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes leppanae</i> Pocock, 1902	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes</i> sp. imm.		NE	
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE
Tetragnathidae	<i>Diphya simoni</i> Kauri, 1950	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leucauge argyrescens</i> Benoit, 1978	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge medjensis</i> Lessert, 1930	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge thomeensis</i> Kraus, 1960	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
Theridiidae	<i>Argyrodes argyrodes</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	0	LC	C
	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phoroncidia capensis</i> (Simon, 1895)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Thomisidae	<i>Ansiae tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014*	4	VU	SAE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phrynarachne rugosa</i> (Latreille, 1804)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema langheldi</i> Dahl, 1907	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema mandibulare</i> Dahl, 1907	2	LC	AE
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema riflense</i> Strand, 1909	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus cancellatus</i> Thorell, 1899	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus natalensis</i> Lessert, 1925	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus tugelanus</i> Lawrence, 1942	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Trachelidae	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trachelas</i> sp.		NE	
Uloboridae	<i>Philoponella angolensis</i> (Lessert, 1933)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
Zodariidae	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE
Zoropsidae	<i>Phanotea cavata</i> Griswold, 1994	4	LC	SAE